

Bridges That Redefine: The Tutoring Role as a Link Between Secondary and Higher Education

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Abstract (extended)

Introduction and core metaphor

This book reflects the role of the tutor in the final years of secondary school, conceptualizing the tutor not only as a guide but as a "bridge" that connects students with higher education. The metaphor of the bridge is central: a bridge is not passive support (like a stake next to a tree) but an active structure that enables passage from one side to another. The tutor as a bridge links the student's present knowledge and perceived limitations with their actual capabilities and future possibilities. Drawing on Antonio Machado's poem ("Wayfarer, there is no path, the path is made by walking"), the book argues that tutoring is an act of creative humanism, where each student challenges the tutor to transform themselves.

The adolescent context

Adolescence is understood as a historical-social-biological construction with symbolic foundations, embedded in a specific era and social stratum. The book warns against homogenizing all young people or reducing youth to a mere transitional category of preparation for adulthood. Many adults believe that adolescents "are still maturing and know nothing about life," a view that, while partially true, denies young people their presence in the present. Some adolescents face early labor insertion or family responsibilities, which reduces their available study time and disrupts the "temporal capital" that adults assume they have in abundance. These precociously assumed roles prevent young people from envisioning mature projects based on their own tastes and interests.

Re-signify learning and motivation

Chapter 1 addresses motivation as a "great engine," understood as a movement toward re-creation of the self when driven by causes that promote passage from one state to another of learning.

Chapter 2 focuses on re-signify learning through project-based work that reflects real problems and interdisciplinary approaches. The book asks: what use is teaching grammatical analysis or percentage problems if the person later cannot calculate a discount or express their need to know it? Conceiving difficulties as opportunities is what sustains the concept of the bridge.

Articulation between secondary and higher education

Chapter 3 analyzes the specific challenges of adapting to higher education, recognizing that this transition involves choices, losses (duels), and emotional management. The lack of articulation between educational levels should not be a cost borne by the student. The book identifies key differences and similarities between secondary and higher education that tutors must understand to facilitate smooth transitions.

Chapter 4 presents self-regulation as an essential capacity for synergistic tutor-student work, developed through metacognition. The tutor never has control over

the student's internal learning process and recognizing this is crucial to avoid confusion: teaching does not guarantee that others learn.

ICT and the digital tutor

Chapter 5 addresses information and communication technologies (ICT) as a necessary language, not merely a modern accessory. The tutor is also a digital being, using cell phones, ATMs, and web-based procedures. Even if the school lacks a state-of-the-art computer lab, tutors must recognize that their own communication methods (chalk, markers) must now coexist with electronic modalities to connect with young people who have a different present and future.

The epilogue: "patient questioning"

The epilogue emphasizes that tutoring should not impose fixed solutions but rather practice "patient questioning" – questions that do not expect immediate or exact answers, because the student may not yet know them. This process helps students discover their self-concept, self-worth, and beliefs, leading to the formation of self-esteem, which is both cognitive and emotional. The tutor's review of their own cliché discourses enables an open, flexible attitude toward conflicts. A stone in the path can be an obstacle, but also an opportunity for analysis or a support to allow passage. The choice of how to face and help the student face problems is part of that review of preconceived ideas.

Final message

The book concludes that bridging secondary and higher education requires an active, forward-looking attitude. The tutor is a privileged actor in articulation between educational levels. A bridge necessarily leads to another side, to new possible goals, and to captivating unknowns waiting to be discovered. The work calls for systemic, organized action that acknowledges both cognitive and emotional dimensions, preparing students not only to enter higher education but to thrive within it. The encounter of two potentialities – learner and educator – is the creation of a bridge that redefines, leaving traces to become better and allowing others to do the same.